

FORMATION OF THE INTERCULTURAL COMPETENCE OF STUDENTS THROUGH USING INTERNET RESOURCES

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Abstract:

This article talks about the formation of the intercultural communication competence of the future foreign language students through Internet resources, and it is mentioned that the order in which they are used will be appropriate for the purpose.

Key words: computer, internet, technology, communication, dialogue, print.

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In recent years in the field of foreign language teaching the question of the importance and expediency of using Internet resources in foreign language education has been increasingly raised, which implies not only analyzing the use of new technical means, but also researching the positive and negative sides of the introduction of innovative forms and methods of teaching.

Modern methods of teaching foreign languages are connected with the ongoing technological progress, as well as with the technological renewal of the learning process. Recent advances in high technology and the spread of the global Internet provide foreign language teachers, methodologists, and students themselves with tremendous opportunities for further improvement of the teaching process.

That is why it is so important to improve the methodology of using computer information technologies in teaching English. Modern information technology is becoming part of the learning process. Computer technologies and the English language class are an actual direction that requires modern approaches and innovative solutions. Modern pedagogical technologies such as collaborative learning, project methods, the introduction of modern information technologies and Internet resources can help bring to life a person-centered approach to learning, provide individualization and differentiation of training, taking into account the capabilities of children and their level of learning.

The idea of introducing Internet technologies in the course of theoretical and practical classes in a foreign language, according to Rober, has been widely spread among teachers, methodologists around the world. The didactic aspects of computerization of education have been developed by well-known scientists and educators E. G. Azimov, B. S. Gershunsky, I. O. Loginov, E. I. Mashbitz, R. P. Mil-rud, E. S. Polat and others. Scientists believe that the expediency of using the Internet is due to the fact that information technology provides a time-and money-saving

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method of learning a foreign language that meets the needs of students in an information society. Web resources provide the opportunity for foreign language learners to be in constant contact with native speakers, up to 24 hours a day, thereby introducing the learner in a continuous process of active use of a foreign language, as well as allowing them to choose the time and place of training, its options, types and even a teacher, a native speaker, depending on the needs of a particular learner.

The possibilities of Internet resources are endless. The universal Internet creates conditions for obtaining any important information for students and teachers from anywhere in the world: country study material, announcements from the life of young people, notes from printed editions and magazines. At English lessons with the help of the Internet you can solve the whole range of didactic tasks: to form reading skills, improve the knowledge of written language, enrich the vocabulary of students, create motivation in teenagers to learn English.

In the recommendations for teachers at Cambridge University, Warschauer states that the Internet is one of the factors contributing significantly to the promotion of the use of computers for language education. According to the scholar, with the appearance of the Internet language learners got a great opportunity to communicate with other students or native speakers of the language being studied all over the world with minimum expenses and time.

In addition, Warschauer highlights one of the advantages of using computers and the Internet in the practice of teaching and learning languages specifically for teachers, arguing that the Internet and live language communication have now become a single process, constantly available to the target audience of foreign language learners.

Nowadays, one of the main advantages of the introduction of web technologies is to provide the teacher with a huge variety of learning resources, materials, technologies through the Internet. It is through the Internet that teachers now have the opportunity to easily obtain various materials for teaching students, as well as discover all the most modern methods of teaching a foreign language.

The use of the Internet in a communicative approach is highly motivated. Its aim is to get students interested in learning a foreign language by building and expanding their knowledge. Students should be prepared to use the language for real communication outside the classroom, for example: when visiting the country of the target language, when hosting foreign guests at home, when corresponding and with students from other countries.

Educational Internet resources should be aimed at comprehensive formation and development:

- aspects of foreign language communicative competence in all variety of its components;
- communicative and cognitive skills to search and select, summarize and classify, analyze the information obtained;
- communicative skills of presenting the results of work with Internet resources;
- ability to use the Internet for self-education with the purpose of acquaintance with cultural-historical heritage of different countries and nations.
- skills to use the resources of the network to meet their information and educational interests and needs.

–It is necessary to show the role of the teacher in the use of Internet resources. The role of the teacher can be changed in the educational process due to new didactic possibilities of using Internet technologies, goals and objectives of education, it is aimed at cooperation and collaboration with students, implementation of joint search and analysis of the results. The teacher rather acts as an adviser, a partner who guides students' activities, promotes their independent research search.

–There are a number of tasks that can be performed with the help of the Internet:

- integrating web materials into the content of the lesson
- self-guided information retrieval by students as part of their project work;
- in-depth independent study of the first or second foreign language, elimination of gaps in knowledge, skills, and abilities;
- self-preparation to pass the qualifying exam as an external student;
- systematic study of a particular aspect of a foreign language at a distance under the guidance of a teacher;
- raising motivation and creating the need to learn a foreign language by means of live communication;
- development of reading skills and abilities, directly using the materials of the network of varying degrees of complexity;
- formation listening skills and abilities on the basis of authentic audio texts of the Internet, also accordingly prepared by the teacher;
- improving monological and dialogical skills based on problem-based discussion of online materials presented by the teacher or a student;
- improving writing skills by responding individually;
- adding vocabulary, both active and passive, with the vocabulary of a modern foreign language, reflecting a certain stage of development of culture of the people, the social and political structure of society, using authentic texts from the country of the studied language;
- acquaintance with cultural knowledge, including speech etiquette, features of speech behavior of different peoples in the conditions of communication, peculiarities of culture, traditions of the country of the studied language.

Speaking about the specific ways of using the possibilities of the Internet in teaching English, the following should be singled out as the most effective:

- participation in telecommunication contests, Olympiads, tests (an opportunity to obtain an objective assessment of knowledge, to self-assert oneself, prepare for exams, participate in other types of contests and Olympiads
- the possibility of prompt free publication of student's creative works (to increase motivation, so necessary for teenagers to assert themselves.
- access to self-education on free or paid distance learning courses, including training in leading foreign educational institutions.

In conclusion, we should emphasize that the Internet provides many opportunities to improve the quality of teaching a foreign language and to create some chances for learning. It can be excellent assistant in the organization of the learning process, namely in teaching various types of speech activity; but despite the many obvious advantages of the Internet, many experts who actively use it in their teaching practice and advocate the introduction of new technologies in the

educational process, emphasize the need for rational, methodologically justified, strictly dosed, proportionally differentiated depending on the aspect and purpose of teaching use of the Internet in the classroom.

The didactic potential of the Internet is very great. It can become a means of achieving educational goals, both for the student and for the teacher. In this case, the teacher becomes an assistant doing the work that is most organic to the modern educational context. The Internet does not replace the teacher but becomes one of the most important means of teaching a foreign language in the modern stage.

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